

Characterization of clayey sludge with potential use in the development of geopolymeric materials

Kelly Viviana Patiño López¹; Estefanía Maya Tobón²; Camilo Rodríguez Salcedo³; Eliana Llano Cardona⁴; Gloria Restrepo⁵
Universidad de Antioquia, Colombia

The environmental issue related to the safe disposal of waste products from industrial activities represents a major societal challenge. Waste generation not only hurts the environment but also affects the competitiveness of the industry and the entire associated value chain. In the extraction process of stone materials, large quantities of clayey sludge are generated daily and must be disposed of properly, generating additional costs. In this study, two types of clayey sludge generated in quarries extracting stone materials were characterized. Both wastes were thoroughly analyzed using analytical and instrumental techniques, as well as methodologies that allowed the identification of their qualities for possible use in the development of polymeric materials. The results of the different analyses led to the conclusion that the residue with the greatest potential for use in the development of these materials is the so-called clayey sludge 1. The use of this residue for the proposed purpose could promote a productive chain between regional industrial sectors. This clay sludge represents an opportunity with an additional differentiating value for its valorization as a secondary raw material in the production of construction materials. In sustainability and circular economy scenarios, the aim is to maintain the value of the products in the economy for as long as possible and, by closing the materials cycle, reduce the generation of waste. Under this approach, waste can make the transition to a resource, losing its status as waste and acquiring the character of raw material for the creation of new technological products.

Keywords: Clay sludge, Geopolymeric materials, Waste products, Industrial activities.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15880671

¹ Chemical Engineer and Master in Engineering. Contact: kelly.patino@udea.edu.co

² Chemical Engineering student. Contact: estefania.mayat@udea.edu.co

³ Mechanical Engineering student. Contact: camilo.rodriguez1@udea.edu.co

⁴ Chemical Engineer and PhD in Materials Engineering. Contact: eliana.llano@udea.edu.co

⁵ Chemical Engineer and PhD in Chemical Sciences. Contact: gloria.restrepo1@udea.edu.co

1. INTRODUCTION

The safe use or disposal of waste generated by industrial activities represents a major environmental challenge for society. This problem not only affects the environment but also the competitiveness of the industry and the entire associated value chain.

In the current context of globalization, social and environmental responsibility, in addition to commitments to international regulations, allows companies and governments to understand that the economic model based on production, consumption, and disposal hinders sustainable social competitiveness.

Mining and quarrying play a crucial role in the productive sector, not only because of the variety of areas they impact but also because of their close relationship with construction. In Colombia, in 2021, 7,905,381 m³ of construction materials (such as sands, gravels, and asphalt) were extracted from quarries [1], of which approximately 10% corresponds to clay sludge, waste with the potential to be reincorporated in new productive cycles.

The physicochemical characterization of the wastes generated in the mining and processing of materials allows evaluating their potential for the development of new materials such as geopolymers used for the manufacture of non-structural building blocks. The valuation of this type of waste represents an opportunity to use it as a second-hand raw material in the manufacture of construction materials. In the context of sustainability and circular economy, the aim is for products to maintain their value in the economy for as long as possible and for waste generation to be minimized at the end of the life cycle of the materials [2].

2. METHOD

The characterization of clayey sludge from material beneficiation quarries was carried out using a combined methodology of consultations and dialogues with the companies producing the sludge, as well as a strategic search for information in scientific databases to support the research. The information obtained was collected, organized, and classified, considering the objectives of the project, including criteria such as the type of research, the year of publication, the wastes evaluated, and the results obtained in each one of them.

2.1 Selection, collection, transport, and storage of samples

The selection of the clayey sludge of interest was carried out through visits to mineral beneficiation quarries, two (2) types of waste were selected, these wastes were identified within the study as Clayey Sludge 1 and Clayey Sludge 2. These wastes were sampled at the exit of the dehydration process implemented in the extraction of stone materials, taking into account protocols for sampling, transportation, coding, and labeling for subsequent technical and safe storage.

2.2 Characterization of samples

To establish a correlation between the physicochemical properties of clayey sludge from quarries and its behavior under different conditions of use, analytical and instrumental techniques, and methodologies were used to determine qualities regarding its use for the development of geopolymer materials. Aspects such as chemical and mineralogical composition, granulometry, crystallinity, and amorphousness are inherent to the reactivity, durability, wear of the product, and potentiality of use. In this sense, the two (2) selected wastes were characterized with the analyses described below.

2.2.1 Physicochemical characterization of samples

- *Water content:* The water content of the sludge was determined by placing the wet material in an oven at $110 \pm 5^\circ \text{C}$ ($230 \pm 9^\circ \text{F}$) and drying it to a constant mass. The mass lost due to drying is considered to be water and the remaining mass corresponds to the dry sample. The water content is calculated by relating the mass of water in the wet sample to the mass of the dry sample. This test is performed under the reference standard INV E-122-13 [3].

- *Organic Matter Content:* The organic matter present in a sample is composed of a microorganism fraction or fresh organic materials and humus. The determination of organic matter is of great importance, since in contact with moisture it expands and generates voids between the particles of the material, weakening its resistance for structural uses. The determination of total organic matter is carried out by different methods, and in the case of clayey sludge, the ignition loss method was used. The reference standard for this analysis was INV E 121-13 [4].
- *Pozzolanic activity:* The pozzolanic activity of the clayey sludge was carried out using Chapelle's method, which allows direct determination of calcium consumption using a chemical reaction with a pozzolanic material in an accelerated manner. In a suspension of 1 g pozzolan / 2 g lime, the lime consumed is calculated by the difference between the lime added and the remaining lime. The procedure includes a blank without pozzolan, which serves as a reference for calculating the lime consumed for pozzolan. The reference standard for the analysis is AFNOR, NF P18-513 [5].
- *Real density of solid materials:* To measure the real density of the sample, a Helium (He) gas pycnometer (Accupyc from Micromeritics) was used, which measures volume and true density using the gas displacement technique. A suitable amount of sample is weighed depending on the material, in an analytical balance, then it is taken to the equipment and the average of the five (5) measurements obtained by the equipment is obtained.
- *pH:* This test provides a measure of the reactivity of the material, establishing its degree of acidity or alkalinity, which has a great influence on its physical, chemical, and biological properties. To determine the pH, the samples were diluted in water and mechanically agitated for thirty minutes, then left to stand for another thirty minutes, and finally, the pH was agitated and measured with a pH meter. The reference standard used was NTC 5264: Soil quality, pH determination [6].
- *Conductivity:* This test measures the content of electrolytes present in the material and which are soluble in water; it is an indicator of soil salinity. The determination of conductivity was carried out using a conductivity meter. Through electrical conductivity measurements, information on the total concentration of ionized components in the soil solution is obtained quickly and accurately. Based on NTC 5596: Soil quality, determination of electrical conductivity [7].
- *Atterberg limits and classification:* The objective of these tests is to know the consistency of the material as a function of moisture content. The plastic limit is the moisture content at the transition point from the semi-solid to the plastic state, while the liquid limit is an index corresponding to the moisture content at which the material passes from a plastic state to a liquid state. The numerical difference between the liquid limit and the plastic limit represents the plasticity index.

The SUCS soil classification system, also known as the Unified Soil Classification System (USCS), is widely used in geotechnical engineering to classify soils. This classification organizes soils into five main types: Gravels (G), Sands (S), Clays (C), Silt (L), and Organics (O). The reference standard for the determination of Atterberg limits is ASTM D4318-00S [8] and the classification was performed by the SUCS method. Standard INV E - 181 - 13 [9].

- *Particle size by laser diffraction:* The particle size distribution and classification (ATP) of the samples was evaluated by laser diffraction technique using the Mastersizer 2000E equipment from Malvern Panalytical, this equipment performs 5 measurements and reports the average of the measurements as the final result. The reference standard for this method of analysis is ISO 13320-1:2020 [10].

2.2.2 Compositional and Morphological Characterization

Based on the results obtained in the physicochemical characterization, the residue with the greatest potential was selected and a compositional and morphological characterization was performed according to the following analyses.

- *X-Ray Fluorescence XRF*: The atomic composition of various chemical elements in the evaluated residues was analyzed by X-ray fluorescence XRF. This analysis consists of the emission of secondary X-rays characteristic of a material that has been excited with high-energy X-rays or gamma rays. This phenomenon is widely used for elemental and chemical analysis, particularly in the investigation of metals, glasses, ceramics, and construction materials. The analyses were performed on a Malvern-PANalytical Model Zetium mineral edition 4kW X-ray fluorescence spectrometer.
- *X-Ray Diffraction XRD*: This instrumental analysis technique is used in the characterization of materials that have a defined crystalline structure. The information obtained from the interaction between X-rays and crystals is based on the diffraction produced by a set of atoms in an ordered arrangement. With this technique it is possible to identify the crystalline structures present in the samples, and through these, the mineralogical composition of the material. The analyses were performed in an X-ray diffractometer XRD Malvern-PANalytical Model Empyeon 2012.
- *Scanning Electron Microscopy SEM-EDS*: This analysis technique allows obtaining micro and nanometer scale images of the particles of the material, which allows evaluating surfaces to study the composition and morphology of the materials. Additionally, the equipment has a built-in Energy Dispersive Spectrometer EDS X-ray detector to identify the energies of the X-rays emitted by the sample and, therefore, to know which chemical elements are present. The equipment used for this analysis was the Scanning Electron Microscope (thermionic) model JEOL-JSM 6490LV.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Physicochemical characterization of samples

The results of the physicochemical characterization of the sludge evaluated are compiled and reported in Table 1. In these results, it can be observed that both sludges present moisture contents close to 30%, which is a typical value for this type of material. On the other hand, it is evident that both materials present low organic matter contents, which is a favorable characteristic for their use in construction materials. Likewise, it can be observed that both materials present alkaline and clayey characteristics that are also favorable for the uses proposed in the study.

Table 1. Results of the physicochemical characterization of clayey mud 1

Test	Result in Clayey mud 1	Result in Clayey mud 2
Water content (%)	29.23	26.84
Organic matter content (%)	1.616	0.940
Pozzolanic activity (mg of Ca(OH) ₂ fixed)	139.42	24.25
Actual density of solid materials (g/cm) ³	2.8789 ± 0.0041	2.8447 ± 0.0019
Hydrogen potential (pH)	8.57	9.38
Conductivity (µS/cm)	130.9	145.5
Liquid limit	38	34
Plastic Limit	25	24
Plasticity index	13	10
SUCS Classification	CL	CL
Description	Low plasticity brown clay	Low plasticity gray clay

Regarding the results obtained in the pozzolanic activity test, it is observed that clayey sludge 1 has a greater capacity to react with lime and fix calcium ions, which shows a greater potential for its incorporation in the development of polymeric materials, compared to clayey sludge 2.

It should be clarified that according to the literature, a material is considered to have high pozzolanic activity if it has values of mg of Ca (OH)₂ fixed, higher than 700 [11], in the case of the materials evaluated, none exceeds this value; however, the result obtained for clayey mud 1 is significantly higher than the result for clayey mud 2.

The laser diffraction particle size test data for clayey mud 1 is presented in Table 2 and the complete particle size distribution can be seen in Figure 1.

Table 2. Results of the particle size distribution of clayey sludge 1

Dispersant: Water	IR dispersant: 1.33	IR Sample: 1.62	Laser obscuration (%): 11.81
D (0.1): 2.228 μ m	D (0.5): 17.142 μ m	D (0.9): 72.351 μ m	Residual (%): 1.276

Figure 1. Particle size distribution of clayey sludge 1

The laser diffraction particle size test data for clayey mud 2 is presented in Table 3 and the complete particle size distribution can be seen in Figure 2.

Table 3. Results of particle size distribution of clayey mud 2

Dispersant: Water	IR dispersant: 1.33	IR Sample: 1.62	Laser obscuration (%): 17.16
D (0.1): 3.084 μ m	D (0.5): 27.049 μ m	D (0.9): 73.187 μ m	Residual (%): 0.776

Figure 2. Particle size distribution of clayey mud 2

Table 4 shows a summary of the results of the average diameter of the evaluated residues. These results show a smaller particle size (average diameter) for clayey sludge 1, taking into account that the particle size is directly related to the pozzolanic capacity of the material, it can be concluded that this material presents a greater potential for its use in the development of polymeric materials concerning clayey sludge 2.

Table 4. Summary of ATP results for the sludge evaluated

	Clayey mud 1	Clayey mud 2
Mean diameter D (0.5) (μ m)	17.142	27.049

Taking into account the results obtained in the physicochemical analyses performed, it is evident that clayey mud 1 has a greater potential for use in the development of polymeric materials; for this reason, the characterization of this material was complemented with compositional and morphological analyses.

3.2 Compositional and morphological characterization

- X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF): The elemental composition of clay mud 1 is reported in Table 5. The results show a high content of Magnesium (Mg) and Silicon (Si), ideal for use as a polymeric material; however, the low content of Alumina suggests the need to adjust its content to achieve an adequate geopolymerization reaction, while highlighting the potential of the material for its use in the development of this type of materials.

Table 5. Results of the composition of clayey mud 1 by XRF

Oxides	% w/w	Oxides	% w/w
MgO	37,59	TiO ₂	0,0877
SiO ₂	37,00	P O ₂₅	0,0459
Fe O ₂₃	9,86	V O ₂₅	0,0095
Al O ₂₃	4,26	ZnO	0,0061
CaO	1,54	WO ₃	0,0061
NiO	0,361	Ag O ₂	0,0058
Cr O ₂₃	0,348	CuO	0,0052
Na O ₂	0,245	SrO	0,0016
MnO	0,164	ZrO ₂	0,0016
K O ₂	0,127	Sc O ₂₃	0,0013
LOI	8,33		

- *X-Ray Diffraction XRD*: Figure 3 shows the diffractogram obtained when analyzing clay mud 1 by XRD, showing, as in the XRF analysis, the higher content of magnesium (Mg) and silicon (Si), forming different crystalline phases such as quartz, lizardite, kaolinite, vermiculite and calcium, including a high percentage of phosphorite composed of iron (Fe), magnesium (Mg) and silicon (Si).

The percentages of the crystalline phases are reported in Table 6. The high content of amorphous material shows its high potential for geopolymerization reactions.

Figure 3. XRD diffractogram of clayey mud 1

Table 6. Results of the crystalline phase composition of clayey mud 1 by XRD.

Name	Composition [%]	Chemical Formula
Quartz	1.2	SiO ₂
Kaolinite 1A	1.6	H ₄ Al O ₂₉ Si ₂
Lizardite 1T	6.3	H ₄ Fe Mg O _{0,1592,8419} Si ₂
Vermiculite 2M	2.9	H Mg O ₂₃₁₂ Si ₄
Talc 1A	5.3	H Mg O ₂₃₁₂ Si ₄
Magnesiohornblende, ferriane	6.9	H _{1,93} Al _{1,54} Ca _{1,6} Fe K Mg _{1,680,083,16} Na O _{0,4424} Si _{6,76} Ti _{0,17}
Forsterite	20.5	Fe Mg O _{0,191,814} Si
Magnetite	0.2	Fe O ₃₄
Amorphous material	55.1	---

- *Scanning Electron Microscopy SEM-EDS*: Figure 4 shows some micrographs of several zones of interest in the clayey mud 1. Particles with cubic shapes are observed, others with elongated shapes and in lamellar layers, with sizes of approximately 30 to 40 μm, and some with agglomerates of nanometric particles on the surface.

The semi-quantitative composition of the sample is reported in Table 7 and the EDS spectrum is in Figure 5. The SEM-EDS compositional results confirm the findings obtained with the XRF and XRD analyses.

Figure 4. SEM micrographs of clay mud 1

Table 7. Results of the semi-quantitative composition of clayey mud 1 by SEM-EDS

Element	Weight	Atomic
C	12,31	19,62
O	41,73	49,96
Mg	17,07	13,45
To	1,31	0,93
Yes	19,21	13,10
K	0,14	0,07
Ca	0,44	0,21
Faith	7,12	2,44
Ni	0,33	0,11
Cu	0,34	0,10
Totals	100,00	100,00

Figure 5. EDS Spectrum - Clay Mud 1

4. CONCLUSIONS

Through the use of advanced analytical and instrumental techniques, precise data on the physicochemical, compositional, and textural properties of two types of clayey sludge from quarries extracting stone materials were obtained. These data allowed a detailed evaluation of the potential of the wastes for applications in the development of polymeric materials.

The results obtained showed that the sludge called Clay Sludge 1 shows superior characteristics in terms of composition and properties that favor its use in the production of polymeric materials. This residue presents a greater aptitude to develop geopolymers due to its specific properties that meet the requirements for this application.

The use of clay sludge in the manufacture of polymeric materials not only represents an effective solution for waste management in quarries but can also encourage the creation of a productive chain between regional industrial sectors. This could foster a circular and sustainable economy, contributing to the development of new products and the reduction of environmental impacts associated with waste disposal.

The results presented in this work are associated with the current need to implement circular economy strategies that promote the valorization of industrial wastes. The findings obtained constitute the starting point for developing more in-depth studies and pilot tests to optimize the process of transforming clay sludge into polymeric materials. Furthermore, it is essential to explore the economic feasibility and scalability of this approach to ensure its effective implementation and long-term benefits.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank the Universidad de Antioquia for their support in carrying out this research.

REFERENCES

- [1] DANE. (2021). Análisis económico y social de la minería en Colombia: retos y oportunidades. Recuperado: <http://www.dane.gov.co/files/investigaciones/planes-departamentos-ciudades/211022-Asociacion-Colombiana-de-Mineria.pdf>
- [2] Eco Inteligencia. (2013). El análisis del ciclo de vida. Recuperado: <https://www.ecointeligencia.com/2013/02/analisis-ciclo-vida-acv/>
- [3] E-122-13. (2012). Determinación en el laboratorio del contenido de agua (humedad) de muestras de suelo, roca y mezclas de suelo -agregado. Recuperado: <https://www.da-lab.co/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/INV-122-13.pdf>
- [4] Invias. (2013). INV E-121-13 Determinación del contenido orgánico en suelos mediante pérdida por ignición. Colombia.
- [5] ICONTEC. (2018). NTC 5264. Calidad de suelo. Determinación del pH. Colombia.
- [6] NTC. (2008). NTC5596 Calidad del suelo. Determinación de la conductividad eléctrica. Bogotá.
- [7] AFNOR (2010). NF P18-513. Métakaolin, addition pouzzolanique pour bétons (Définitions, Spécifications, Critères de conformité). Normes Françaises et Européennes.
- [8] ASTM. (2000). D4318-00S Standard Test Methods for Liquid Limit, Plastic Limit, and Plasticity Index of soils. Pensilvania.
- [9] Invias. (2012). INV E-181-13 Sistema Unificado de Clasificación de Suelos para propósitos de ingeniería-SUCS. Recuperado: <https://www.da-lab.co/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/INV-181-13.pdf>
- [10] ISO. (2020). ISO 13320-1:2020 Análisis del tamaño de partículas. Métodos de difracción láser. Ginebra.
- [11] Ferraz E. et al. (2015). Pozzolanic activity of metakaolins by the French standard of the modified Chapelle test: A direct methodology. *Acta Geodynamica et Geomaterialia* 12, 289-298.